

SensorNetGuard: Leveraging Deep Learning for Anomaly Detection in IoT Networks of Autonomous Electric Vehicles

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Abstract—It is crucial to protect the integrity and security of devices such as autonomous electric vehicles or self-driving cars, as they became common nowadays and support the internet of things (IoT). This research presents a novel method for detection in IoT networks of AEVs called SensorNetGuard, which makes use of deep learning techniques. By combining supervised and unsupervised learning methods, SensorNetGuard increases the network's resistance to intrusion and attacks by detecting abnormal activity in real-time. SensorNetGuard detects departures from typical behavior patterns by evaluating data streams from several sensors integrated into AEVs. This allows for a timely reaction to possible security breaches. We use five deep learning model: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to detect the sensors whether they are malicious or not.

Index Terms—Regulatory Compliance, Deep learning, Broadcasting, Emergency Alert, AEVs, Safety

I. INTRODUCTION

Self-driving cars, also known as autonomous vehicles (AVs), it is the important development in transportation sector. These type of vehicles can navigate roadways on their own due to sensors like GPS, radar, cameras and lidar which are combined with robust artificial intelligence algorithms. The claim put out is that they may enhance accessibility and mobility by the AV's supporters. Also claim put out is that it may lowering traffic accidents, carbon emissions and congestion. However, there are many issues remain like ensuring security and accuracy, privacy, job displacement in industries that depend on Driven by humans. That's why people in general need to understand the consequences of these type of vehicles.

Self-driving cars depends on autonomous sensors that is capable to detect the surrounding environment without any human intervention. Modern technologies such as radar, camera, light detection and ranging, ultrasonic sensors, GPS receivers all these are part of these sensors. Cameras are used to detect and understand road signs, traffic signals, obstacles, and other moving vehicles by collecting visual data. GPS receivers provide accurate location data, helping in navigation and route planning. Ultrasonic sensors identify the boundaries and perform low-speed tasks like parking. Radar system uses radio waves to keep track of object's distance and speed from the other vehicles. These all multiple sensors are used in self-driving cars that allows cars to accurately evaluate the surrounding environment and make decisions accurately.

Autonomous Sensors are defined as eyes and ears of the autonomous vehicles because they allows to see and hear the surrounding environment. They are also considered as visual brain of these vehicles. They are capable of determine difficult weather situations like dense fog or torrential rain—radar devices supplement this visible data. IoT also known as Internet of Things, is a vast network of interdependent devices. These devices are capable of collecting and sharing the data through internet. These devices contains sensors, software, and other technologies. IoT devices may improve convenience, efficiency, and automation in a variety of areas of life. IoT devices collect data from surrounding environment and transfer this data to other devices for management using sensors. This sharing of data enables remote control, intelligent decision-making, real-time monitoring etc. IoT devices plays a major role in different sectors such as healthcare, transportation, agriculture, smart homes.

In this research paper, we present SensorNetGuard, a novel architecture which aims is to resolve the crucial problem of identifying malicious sensors activity in context of self-driving vehicles. we are using cutting-edge deep learning algorithms, By using SensorNetGuard we want to improve data reliability by identifying malicious activities. Autonomous vehicles can improve their decision-making capabilities and guarantee dependability and operational safety in real-world driving situations by putting this framework into practice. We see SensorNetGuard as having a major influence on how self-driving technology develops in the future, opening the door to more dependable and safe transportation systems that put everyone's safety and well-being firsts.

Xiaomei Zhang [3] proposes a novel anomaly detection model that combines continuous wavelet transform (CWT) and convolutional neural network (CNN) for in-vehicle networks, aiming to detect malicious behaviors and improve accuracy in identifying vehicle anomalies. The model utilizes CWT to calculate wavelet coefficients for constructing vehicle state images, capturing both time and frequency domain characteristics of the raw data. The model utilizes CWT to calculate wavelet coefficients for constructing vehicle state images, capturing both time and frequency domain characteristics of the raw data, and then employs an optimized CNN to analyze the two-dimensional continuous wavelet transform scalogram (CWTS) as input. Experimental results demonstrate

the superior performance of the proposed model in detecting various vehicle anomalies, with an average accuracy and F1 score improvement of 2.51% and 2.46% respectively compared to related works.

Sahaya, Beni[6]The paper proposes a Hybrid Deep Anomaly Detection (HDAD) approach for effective anomaly detection and cyber-attack mitigation in Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) in the 6G-V2X environment. The HDAD approach operates over the 6G network, providing a swift and accurate anomaly detection mechanism to combat new-age cyber-attacks. The results of the study demonstrate that the HDAD approach has an 8.2 % higher accuracy rate compared to existing systems, highlighting its effectiveness in detecting anomalies and mitigating cyber-attacks in AVs.

Fatemeh Esmaeili[4]Anomaly detection is crucial in sensor signal processing, and deep learning autoencoder-based neural networks are effective for addressing imbalanced datasets. The study developed prediction models using autoencoder networks and kernel density estimation to automatically detect anomalous data recorded by electrochemical aptasensors. The accuracy of the prediction models varied depending on the type and amount of normal data used for training, with the integrated model of unidirectional long short-term memory (ULSTM) and vanilla autoencoder achieving approximately 80% accuracy for the dataset with lengthier signals.

Kyle DeMedeiros[7]The paper provides a survey of anomaly detection in IoT and sensor networks, highlighting the use of machine learning and deep learning techniques for this purpose. It aims to identify anomaly detection approaches, gaps in research, and the importance of anomaly detection in the context of the growing number of Internet-connected devices and the transition to smart infrastructure.

Ning Zhang[5]The paper proposes an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) framework for connected autonomous vehicles (CAVs) to detect anomalies and attacks on the Controller Area Network (CAN) using temporal correlation of message contents. The IDS framework utilizes two prediction modules, LSTM and ConvLSTM, to predict time series data and messages, respectively, and classifies attacks based on prediction errors using a Gaussian Naïve Bayes classifier. The proposed method outperforms other state-of-the-art one-class classifiers and achieves high accuracy in detecting attacks on the CAN bus.

Zhitao He[8]Connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) rely on the security, accuracy, and stability of sensor readings and network data, and abnormal sensor readings can have devastating consequences. The proposed WKN-OC method uses a Wavelet Kernel Network with Omni-Scale Convolutional (WKN-OC) to detect anomalies in intelligent transportation systems (ITS). It focuses on high-frequency components of input data and extracts valuable features through a feature extraction framework, resulting in strong anomaly detection performance. The method achieves 96.78% average accuracy in mixed anomaly experiments and 96.13% accuracy in multi-anomaly experiments, demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting various types of anomalies in the Internet of Vehicles (IoVs) context.

Arti Rana[2]The paper proposes a new intrusion detection model for IoT networks based on anomalies, using deep learn-

ing techniques, to address the increasing cyberattacks on IoT devices. The proposed model achieves good performance in terms of precision, f1-score, recall, and accuracy, as validated using the IoT-23 intrusion detection dataset.

Ujjwal Sachdeva[1]Anomaly detection in IoT sensor data is a crucial research area due to noise, unavailability of labels, high correlation between data points, and the high volume and velocity of data generated by sensors. Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Autoencoders, LSTM Autoencoder, and LSTM Recurrent Neural Networks (LSTM-RNN), are gaining attention for their ability to perform unsupervised learning on high volume data and achieve high detection accuracy for anomalies in time series IoT sensor data. The paper proposes to study and compare the performance of these DL models using simulations conducted on Intel Berkeley Research Labs (IBRL) Sensor data. The results of the simulations will provide insights into the detection accuracy and training time of each DL model, helping researchers choose the most effective method for anomaly detection in time series IoT sensor data.

A. Research Contributions

The paper discusses significant modifications in the field of malicious sensor node detection through the utilization of different LSTM architectures. • This accomplished sensorNetGuard approach seamlessly integrates comprehensive sensor data monitoring for security and safety. • The pre-trained models are ann and cnn. • A detailed analysis of a variety of training preferences, accuracy measures, loss curves, and performance metrics, such as recall and precision, as well as a confusion matrix, were all components of the evaluation process of sensorNetGuard

B. Organization of the paper

The succeeding sections of this paper are assembled as follows: section 2 of this paper exposes the system model and problem formulation, followed by section 3 that the subsequent section 4 which elaborates on the performance of the paper which is followed by a conclusion and future work in section 5.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Within the domain of advanced Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, the task of identifying sensor Malicious behaviour within vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs) is tackled with efficacy and precision. Harnessing features like Node ID, Timestamp, Packet Rate, Packet Drop Rate, Data Throughput, Signal Strength, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), Battery Level, Energy Consumption Rate, Route Request Frequency, Route Reply Frequency, Data Transmission Frequency, Data Reception Frequency, Error Rate, CPU Usage, Memory Usage, Bandwidth, and the Is Malicious indicator, system model aims to fortify VANETs resilience against malicious interference.

The dataset utilized for model training and evaluation encompasses samples collected from diverse VANET scenarios, each symbolically represented as S in Equation 1:

$$S = \{s1, s2, \dots, sn\}$$

The malicious sensor Detection framework is structured with multiple layers of interconnected neurons, constituting a comprehensive architecture denoted as:

$$N = \{L1, L2, \dots, Ln\}$$

where n represents the total number of layers in the network.

Despite the effectiveness of ANNs, CNNs, and LSTMs in diverse tasks, the issue of overfitting can diminish model performance. To counteract this, regularization techniques such as L1 regularization are incorporated into the model architecture. By penalizing large weights, these regularization techniques mitigate overfitting and enhance model generalization.

$$\text{L1 regularization term} = \lambda \sum_i |w_i|$$

Where:

λ is the regularization parameter controlling the strength of regularization, λ represents the regularization parameter governing the strength of regularization, and w_i signifies individual weights within the model. By integrating regularization techniques into the ANN, CNN, and LSTM models, the algorithms' robustness and generalization capabilities are fortified, ensuring accurate detection of malicious activities within VANET environments.

III. DATA PRECUREMENT LAYER

In this section, we have described our approach: data collection, data preprocessing, LSTM layer, and decision-making layer. These are all step-by-step procedures given in fig 1 so that we are able to achieve greater accuracy. In this, we have used the LSTM model, in which we get the highest accuracy compared to other models like ann and cnn. For reference, we are giving you the diagram of how our model actually works and goes through each step.

A. Data Procurement Layer

1) The study of the dataset given in [9] is composed of various parameters obtained from the sensor; the selection of this dataset due to the sensor values is more accurate and precise. It has real time values.

2) dataset size: The parameters or we can say features are contained in the data set, which includes 10000 data points from real sensors. Including Time, Packet Rate, Packet Drop Rate, Data Throughput, Signal Strength, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), Battery Level, Energy Consumption Rate, Route Request Frequency, Route Reply Frequency, Data Transmission Frequency, Data Reception Frequency, Error Rate, CPU Usage, Memory Usage, Bandwidth, and the Is Malicious indicator in which it is divided into two classes: the actual data and the target variable scenario. The target variable consists of its own class.

Scenario 1 (No Attack): In this scenario we identify there is an absence of a jammer but there exists a source of

unintentional interference that impacts the communication between the two autonomous electric car' Network.

Scenario 2 (Attack): The scenario system can find the presence of a jammer that initiates following the target from an initial position (specified as one of sensor node detected malicious) while simultaneously transmitting jamming signals.

while the processing of the model there are 10000 data points from all the sensors, of which 20 percentage are used as training data. During model training, this distribution allows for both classes to be adequately represented.

3) Data Quality: The performance of predictive models depends on ensuring the quality and reliability of the gathered data. Quality control tests and validation by drop of time and ip address and all to get the best quality of data to give to the model and train the model.

B. Data preprocessing layer

In the preprocessing the implemented code, data preprocessing serves as a pivotal phase which help at enhancing the quality and Correspondence of the input data for subsequent deep learning model training or can say LSTM training model. The below steps outline the comprehensive data preprocessing pipeline:

The initial step involves loading the dataset using the provided file path. The dataset include all the features and a target variable which is essentially needed for model training and evaluation.

After, loading the dataset's features and the according target variable are separated.split into training and testing sets. This segregation facilitates focused more on preprocessing and model training.

$$A = N_{\text{train}} = 0.8 \cdot (X_{\text{train}} + y_{\text{train}})$$

$$B = N_{\text{test}} = 0.2 \cdot (X_{\text{test}} + y_{\text{test}})$$

To resolve the potential class imbalance within the training dataset, random oversampling is employed in that's why the code using the RandomOverSampler class .

$$\theta_{\text{sampled}} = X_{\text{train sampled}} + Y_{\text{train sampled}}$$

This technique aims to increase the representation of minority class instances by randomly duplicating samples, thus achieving a more balanced training dataset.

$$\Omega_{\text{re sampled}} = \theta_{\text{sampled}}$$

C. Deep learning layer

LSTM models, renowned for their prowess in capturing temporal relationships in sequential data, find poignant application in the domain of automatic self-driving car networks. Consider a scenario where an autonomous vehicle navigates through urban environments, relying heavily on its sensory inputs to make split-second decisions regarding navigation, hazard detection, and collision avoidance. In this context, LSTM architectures serve as the backbone of the vehicle's neural network, enabling it to effectively interpret and respond to the dynamic flow of information from various sensors. For instance, when encountering a complex fluctuation in data intersection, the LSTM model seamlessly integrates inputs from the vehicle's sensors over time, enabling it to discern

Fig. 1: The proposed approach.

intricate patterns of vehicle movements. Moreover, LSTM's inherent capability to retain information from past inputs while processing real-time data proves invaluable in scenarios requiring nuanced understanding of temporal dynamics. For example, ensuring smooth and safe navigation through the bend. Furthermore, the adaptability of LSTM models to handle inputs of variable length is exemplified in scenarios where the duration and frequency of sensor observations vary. For instance, when navigating through dense urban environments with sporadic GPS signal availability, the LSTM model dynamically adjusts its processing to accommodate intermittent data streams, ensuring continuous and reliable navigation. Importantly, the integration of CNNs and attention mechanisms alongside LSTM architectures enhances the vehicle's ability to detect and respond to potential hazards in real-time. For example, by combining LSTM's temporal processing capabilities with CNN's spatial feature extraction, the vehicle can accurately identify attack and system get aware from this. In essence, LSTM models play a pivotal role in enabling autonomous vehicles to navigate complex real-world environments with precision and safety. By leveraging detect malicious sensor node to dynamic input scenarios, LSTM-powered self-driving car networks promise to revolutionize the future of vehicle net guard, ushering in an era of enhanced safety on our roads.

$$Y = \sum((\prod f_i(W_i^{(h_{t-1}, x_t)})) \cdot b_i)$$

where :

represents the predicted output, function f_i : $f_1, f_2, f_2 \dots f_n$. is different layer use in model, w_i : $w_1, w_2, w_3 \dots w_n$. represents the weights of the i -th layer, b_i : $b_f, b_i, b_c \dots b_n$. represents the biases of the i -th layer $[h_{t-1}, x_t]$ denotes the concatenation of the current input and the previous hidden state of input features.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (TP_i + FP_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n TP_i}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (TP_{sci} + FN_{sci})}{\sum_{i=1}^n TP_{sci}}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n TP_i + TN_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n (TP_i + FP_i + TN_i + FN_i)}$$

$$\text{F1 score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

where :

TP stands for True Positives, which are the number of correctly predicted positive instances. TN stands for True Negatives, which are the number of correctly predicted negative instances. FP stands for False Positives, which are the number of incorrectly predicted positive instances. FN stands for False Negatives, which are the number of incorrectly predicted negative instances. Acc denotes Accuracy, which measures the overall correctness of the model's predictions across all classes. n represents the total number of classes.

D. Decision Making Layer

The Decision Making Layer involves the binary classification of is sensor malicious in AEVs IoT, coupled with the utilization of the model's outcomes in the identification of sensor data for attacked. The sigmoid activation function is employed for binary classification, producing output values between 0 and 1, signifying the probabilities for both classes. The classification formula is given

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

where, $e = 2.71 \times$ is the input value The values predicted by the model are either 1 signifying the malicious sensor found attack happens or 0, indicating the absence, represented by the symbolic notation Y_{pred}

Decision Making Layer:

$$Y_P = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{is malicious} \\ 0 & \text{not malicious} \end{cases}$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Performance evaluation

This section delves into a comprehensive evaluation and comparison of the five Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures employed for training the model.

Fig. 2: performance evaluation

Evaluating the performance of each architecture involves assessing metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 score, which are crucial for determining the efficacy of the models in classifying sensor data. By plotting these metrics on various graphs, a clearer understanding emerges regarding the selection and adoption of the most suitable architecture for the task at hand.

Model	Accuracy score	Precision score	Recall	F1 score
ANN	0.9608	0.9542	0.9608	0.9535
CNN	0.9856	0.9851	0.9849	0.9856
LSTM	0.9909	0.9909	0.9909	0.9909

TABLE I: Performance evaluation table

Validation loss is the measure of how optimal the model is in generalizing the testing data, the decreasing of validation loss on plotting indicates the ability of the model to improve predictions on the testing data or on data which was not used for training. Fig 3(a) shows the plotting of a validation loss curve comparing all the models based on their validation loss values as we plot the loss they identified over each epoch. By observation, we identify LSTM model has a decent decreasing loss and also tends to give the lowest validation

Training loss over epochs significant metric that determines the accuracy of the model's prediction on training data, doing this which indicates how well the model generalizes when fed training input. Now, it is an important measure to take into consideration to prevent the model from overfitting, a common issue arising from high variance and low bias. The graph presented in Fig 3(b) illustrates the training loss across different models, we can observed that LSTM architecture showcasing commendable performance characterized by low training loss.

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve stands as a foundational technique in the domain of multiclass classification models, functioning as a graphical representation of the model's performance across various classification

thresholds. Within the preliminary phase of this investigation, LSTM model emerged with the highest validation accuracy coupled with the lowest validation loss. In Fig 4, we present the ROC curve for the LSTM model, delineating the True Positive Rate along the y-axis and the False Positive Rate along the x-axis. Notably, the ROC curve for the RNN model exhibits a discernible upward trajectory, signifying its efficacy in discriminating between positive and negative cases. Specifically, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) for class 0 is recorded at 0.99, while for class 1 it attains values of 0.99, further accentuating the robust discriminatory capabilities inherent within the model. This empirical evidence underscores the model's aptitude in delineating between distinct types of attacks, showing its potential in distinguishing between different types of attacks

Accuracy, serving as a pivotal metric, delineates the proportion of correctly predicted attack classes relative to the total instances of a particular attack type, thereby illuminating the overarching correctness of our model's predictions. Precision, on the other hand, illuminates the accuracy of positive predictions, furnishing nuanced insights into the model's capability in discerning true positives from false positives. Meanwhile, recall elucidates the extent to which the model effectively identifies the entirety of relevant targets within the dataset. The F1 score, a harmonious amalgamation of precision and recall, encapsulates the holistic efficacy of our model's predictive capabilities. It can be concluded that LSTM architecture has exceeded all the other models in all the parameters used having an accuracy of 0.9991 while CNN had an accuracy of 0.9856 making it the second-best choice and also ANN has accuracy 0.9608. Not only in accuracy but also in precision, recall, and f1 score curve .

Finally, a confusion matrix is employed as a performance testing tool, offering insights into the accuracy of the classification model. This matrix visually represents the model's predictive accuracy across different classes, aiding in the comprehensive assessment of model performance in real-world scenarios. It displays the number of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. True Positives are the instances where the model correctly predicts the positive cases, while Instances where the LSTM accurately predicts negative cases are True Negatives. False Positives represent the instances where the model incorrectly predicts the positive cases and False negatives represent the incorrect predictions of negative cases. In Fig 5, we made Confusion matrices for LSTM algorithms and careful observation highlighted LSTM have the ability to accurately classify cases and enhance the model's performance. There are 82 cases where the model incorrectly predicted in this case for actual 1 where predicted 0 which we tried to get lowest through our approach. The false negatives always tend to be zero in standard cases but the lowest we could get through our approach was 82 cases. So, there are total 2418 cases were identified where the model predicted the model found attack and get malicious node in this there are 2378 for not malicious and for sensor is malicious there are 40.

V. CONCLUSION

From above research we turns out that the study explored deep learning techniques for Vehicular Ad-hoc Network

(a) Validation loss over epochs

(b) Training loss over epochs

Fig. 3

(a) ROC curve

(b) Precision-recall curve

Fig. 4

Fig. 5: Confusion matrix

(VANET) RF jamming detection. After proper study, problem identifying and analyze, it comes to the conclusion that LSTM model is the most successful in terms of accuracy around 99% that is one of the highest accuracies and also LSTM model has the lowest training and validation loss as compared to other models for identifying malicious sensor nodes. Our complete review technique of SensorNetGuard includes

critical indicators including accuracy, F1 scores, recall, and precision. The subsequent efforts may involve the integration of ensemble technologies to improve the predicted accuracy of malicious node identification on AEVs networks. This fulfillment puts more emphasis on how deep learning approaches, in particular LSTM, may improve VANET security and resistance against jamming attacks.

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